

Research

Negotiating Gender Inequality: A Semiotic Analysis of Pakistani Cartoons and Illustrations

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze the Pakistani cartoons and Illustrations that represent gender inequality. This study follows qualitative research methodology. For the analysis of cartoons and illustrations, the Semiotic model by Roland Barthes has been used.

Keywords: Semiotic analysis, Cartoons, Roland Barthes, Gender Inequality

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Introduction

Cartoons are defined as a type of visual art that are usually created in unrealistic or semi-realistic style. It is a drawing that is meant to be humorous, caricatured, or satirical. When someone mentions cartoons, it is typically taken to be something that is solely related to children. However, recent studies have revealed that in addition to being able to amuse, they are also capable of communicating some of the most complicated ideas to the intended audience. Nelson (1975) asserts that cartoons are the perfect medium for communicating complicated ideas and subtle messages, which is why viewers typically find them to be highly appealing.

Semiotic Analysis: Semiotics is a branch of linguistics that deals with the study of signs. Unlike other discourse forms, analyzing visuals or visual discourse requires a distinct theoretical framework. For this reason, Semiotics is regarded as a reliable theoretical and methodological foundation.

Among various semiotic models, the semiotic model by Roland Barthes, which is primarily based on two notions: **denotation** and **connotation**, has been utilized in this research.

Denotation: The denotative level, sometimes referred to as the first level of signification in Barthes' semiotic theory, is associated with the denotative meaning or the "literal meaning" of the given word or sign.

Connotation: Connotative meaning, which is often considered as secondary or additional meaning, is the second level of signification in the Barthes' theory.

Research Objective

1. To investigate the connotative meanings of the selected Pakistani cartoons and Illustrations.

Research Question

1. What are the connotative meanings of the selected Pakistani cartoons and Illustrations and how they portray gender inequality?

Literature Review

According to (Test, 1991) Cartoon is a genre that can be characterized by the hilarious way in which events are depicted, making use of irony and satire to expose, mock, and attack in a playful, witty, and artistic manner.

Cartoons are a collection of symbols... that mean different things to different people (Lang et al., n.d., p. 21). This is to say that the meaning behind them is understood based on your understanding regarding what is being shown in the cartoons. Morris (1992 as cited in Tariq et al., 2016) stated that “A cartoon is a weapon in the hands of the cartoonist, who can hit whatever he feels like followed by freedom of speech (p.78).

Research Methodology

For the current study, the qualitative approach has been used. According to Cresswell (1998:5) Qualitative approach can be undertaken when there is a need to present a detailed view of a topic. The data has been collected from the official websites and pages of different Pakistani Cartoonists and Illustrators.

Sampling: For the sampling, the purposive sampling has been used in the current study. Purposive sampling is a type of non-probability sampling where the researcher selects the sample based on a variety of characteristics. The sample collected for the study was the cartoons based on gender inequality. The sample was collected from the official pages of different Pakistani cartoonists and illustrators.

Data collection and analysis:

The data has been collected from the websites and official social media pages of different Pakistani Cartoonists and Illustrators. For the analysis. The semiotic model by Roland Barthes has been used. This semiotic model is primarily based on two notions: **denotation** and **connotation**.

Findings and Discussion

Figure no. 1

By: Wasfa Kamal

SIGN

DENOTATION

CONNOTATION

Several boys
and a girl

A young girl is shown attempting to reach where the boys are but is unsuccessful.

It is depicting the gender inequality in terms of education in Pakistan.

Denotation:

A girl is shown making an unsuccessful attempt to reach where the boys are. The linguistic message in the cartoon is "Don't leave me behind"

Connotation: This is a portrayal of gender disparity in terms of education that exists in Pakistan. The linguistic message "Don't leave me behind" represents that Pakistani women are left behind in all walks of life including the education. In this cartoon, the boys are depicted as being on top, while the girl tries to get there, but her efforts are proved to be unsuccessful. It relates to the fact that despite their best efforts, women in Pakistan are unable to reach to where the men are for a variety of reasons. According to a survey, Pakistan ranked 144th out of 156 countries in terms of educational attainment. According to Bari (2005) Women's education benefits society and the family in the long run, but they have fewer chances than men in all areas of life, such as the economics, politics, and **education** (Daraz, 2012; Bari, 2005)

Figure no 2.

By: Nigar Nazar

SIGN	DENOTATION	CONNOTATION
A Man and a Girl	The man is responding to the questions asked by a girl.	The man is depicted as A Maulvi. (A religious individual)

Denotation: A man is shown responding to the young woman, who appears to be writing down his comments in her diary. This is a captioned-cartoon that contains a number of sentences.

Connotation: For the image to communicate to the recipient (its viewer), Barthes claims that it must have a structural independence connected to what is ideological and aesthetic. The recipient can then interpret the image on a connotative level based on his or her cultural and symbolic background. In this cartoon by Nigar Nazar, the man has been depicted as a religious figure which is signified from the cap he is wearing (taqiyah) which is worn by Muslim men. He also has

a beard, which is another sign of his depiction as a Maulvi (a religious figure). The girl appears to be questioning him about the girls' education. The linguistic message in this cartoon contains the following captions:

Man: Women should be imparted enough education to be able to read the QURAN.

Girl: What else should they read besides QURAN?

Man: Religious books

Girl: Why are you opposed to formal education for women?

Man: They are more intelligent and they surpass us, MEN.

This cartoon represents the opinions of the typical religious men in Pakistan on girls' education. Gender inequality in Pakistan is a major problem that also affects girls' access to education. The linguistic message "They are more intelligent and they surpass us, men" is alluding to the perspective some people hold about girls' education. Women in Pakistan are often discouraged from going to school under the assumption that their education may be useless as they will eventually have to get married and focus solely on taking care of the home and their children. According to UN Women, In Pakistan, 53.6% of women lack access to **education**, training, and work.

Figure no 3

By: Mahmood Ahmad

SIGN	DENOTATION	CONNOTATION
Girl	A girl with injury marks all over her face, hands, and neck is carrying a smiling picture of herself in her hands.	This is a depiction of domestic violence and is alluding to the domestic abuse faced by women.

Denotation: A young lady is seen carrying a picture of herself that was clicked on the day she graduated. Her face, neck, and hands are covered in countless injury marks which is signifying the domestic violence. The text on the image is written in Urdu. (National Language of Pakistan) that says: "Aakhir Kab Tak Main Seeriyon Se Girti Rahongi" – *Until when will I keep falling down the stairs.*

Connotation: This is a portrayal of domestic violence and is alluding to the domestic abuse faced by women in Pakistan. Gender inequality is strongly related with various forms of violence, including domestic violence. The linguistic message "Aakhir Kab Tak Main Seeriyon Se Girti Rahongi, which is written on the image in the Urdu language, can be translated in English as "Until when will I keep falling down the stairs" This is a reference to the justifications girls

use to conceal their struggles from their families and society for the sake of honor. According to (Ibrahim, 2005: 2), when males who have control over women's physical being abuse them, such as their fathers, brothers, spouses, and male relatives, they are unable to speak out about it. The girl's physical characteristics in this illustration, which includes her injuries, the background, and her smiling picture all are constructing its connotative meaning. The smiling photo she is holding in her hands reveals that she is a graduate and had previously been happy with her life. (Ali, 2001: 8) stated the majority of Pakistani women experience abuse or fear of violence every day, whether at home, in the workplace, or in public places. Women in Pakistan have spoken out about being abused physically, mentally, and sexually by their partners.

Conclusion

The aim of the study was to analyze the connotative meanings in the Pakistani cartoons and Illustrations. The findings reveal that the cartoons depicted a variety of forms of gender inequality which includes: gender disparity in terms of education, and domestic violence. Various forms of violence, including domestic violence, have a strong relationship with gender disparity. The connotative and denotative meanings along with the linguistic messages were analyzed. It is concluded that today cartoons have developed into a powerful genre used as a medium to convey the most complex ideas and messages.

References

- Creswell, J. W. 1998. *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five designs*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Lang, K. et al. (n.d.). *Understanding the world of political cartoons for educators*. World Affairs Council Global Classroom. Seattle Times Company Newspapers. *Newspapers in Education*
- Nelson, R. (1975). *Cartooning*. Retrieved from <https://www.goodreads.com>
- Tariq et al (2016). *Cartoon war...a political dilemma! A semiotic analysis of political cartoons*.
- Test, G. (1991). *Satire: spirit and art*: University of South Florida Press (Tampa).
- Journal of Media Studies* Vol. 31(1): February 2016 74-92. ICS Publications. Retrieved from http://pu.edu.pk/images/journal/ICS/PDF/05_31_1_16.pdf last April 2, 2020.

